

MOLECULAR BIOLOGY

MORPHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF EXTRAORGANIC ARTERIAL VESSELS OF SPINAL GANGLIA. LIGHT AND ELECTRON MICROSCOPIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Generally, the function of each organ depends on its structural peculiarities, especially on vascularization. The aim of the present study was to investigate the morphological feature of extraorganic (extracapsular) arterial vessels of spinal ganglia. Experiment performed on white male rats in Science Research laboratory of Azerbaijan Medical University. As a result, despite to general rules, the research show that arterial vessels placed in connective tissue elements surrounding the spinal ganglia not accompanied by corresponding venous vessels; extraorganic arterial vessels have the ability to adjust arterial pressure conditions, to transport vasoactive metabolites, by regulation contraction of smooth muscle cells to change the dimensions of the vascular lumen.

Keywords: spinal ganglia, vessels, endothelial cell, smooth muscle cells, ultrastructure.

Introduction. In order to clarify the characteristics of flow of biological fluids in organs, it is important to elucidate the mutual histotopography and ultrastructural peculiarities of the vessels involved in their blood supply and in transport of interstitial fluid. From this point of view, there are necessary to learn in detail the extraorganic and intraorganic vessels of spinal ganglia. Spinal ganglia is very important part of peripheral nervous system. It contains thousands of sensory neurons that transmit information from outer and inner environment to the central nervous system. This includes signals related to proprioception, temperature, and nociception [1, 2]. Histotopographically the spinal ganglia are situated outside of the blood brain barrier. In this regard, molecules circulating in the vascular system can directly access to the it. Cell body of primary sensory neurons composing the spinal ganglia have high sensitivity to substances, molecules, neurotoxic agents. That's why to study peculiarities of extraorganic vascular organization in spinal ganglia is very significance [3]. It should be noted that studying structural peculiarities of extraorganic and intraorganic vessels of spinal ganglia playing important role in formation of neuropathic pains of different origins is of particular importance [4, 5].

Aim. The purpose of the research work was to study the histotopography, composition and morphological feature of the extraorganic vessels of spinal ganglia.

Material and methods. The object of research is spinal ganglia taken from 20 white rats weighing 200-220 gr. The animals fed in Science Research laboratory in specific pathogen conditions. All procedures of experiments performed in accordance with the Principles of Laboratory and Animal Care established by the Azerbaijan Medical University. Epon-araldite blocks of 10 rat ganglia were prepared after fixation by intravascular perfusion with 2,5% glutaraldehyde solution. Semithin (1-2 μm) sections obtained from the indicated blocks on LKB-III, Leica EM UC7 ultratome were stained with methylene blue, azure II and basic fuchsin [6]. After fixation of 10 other white rats, into the same catheter was administered ink solution dissolving in 10% gelatin until it outflow from the vena cava inferior, and the object of research was taken together with the structures in close proximity from both side (spinal roots, spinal nerve), then fixed in 10% formalin solution, frozen in a cryostat, and were obtained total sections with a thickness of 100-150 μm . Both semithin and total sections were inspected under a Latimet (Leitz) light microscope and pictures of the necessary parts were taken with a Pixera digital camera system.

Ultrathin sections (70-100 nm) gotten from Epon-araldite blocks were stained in uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate solutions [7]. Electronograms were analyzed under 80-120kv voltage and studied in a JEM-1400 transmission electron microscope.

Results. The results of the conducted research show that both arteries and arterioles located within the connective tissue elements surrounding the spinal ganglia are not accompanied by corresponding venous vessels.

The cryostatic section of spinal ganglion vessels were revealed with the ink solution (dissolved in 10% gelatin) injected into the ascending aorta after fixation by the perfusion method shown on figure 1A. On center of slide clearly visible extracapsular network (ECN) composing arterial, venous vessels and also capillaries. That network participated in vascularization of spinal

ganglia and source for intraganglionic network of organ.

Under light microscope on histological slide clearly demonstrated the extraorganic arterial vessels in all Figure 1 (B, C, D) not accompanied by corresponding venous vessels. There are arterial vessels on slide 1B (shown by Ar) with 16 μ m thickness wall, that is characterized by thin tunica intima formed by endothelial cells, a middle layer- tunica media, composing several layers of smooth muscle cells, and outer layer-tunica adventitia consisting of connective tissue elements. Nearby sharply seen small sized its branch arteriole (indicated by P) - named as precapillary arteriole. Despite the diameter of only 8,14 μ m, the wall of the precapillary arteriole is thick (due to the presence of primitive smooth muscle cells in the composition).

Figure 1. A - Cryostatic section of spinal ganglion vessels were revealed with the ink solution (dissolved in 10% gelatin) injected into the ascending aorta after fixation by the perfusion method; B, C, D - Microscopic images of vessels involved in the organization of the extracapsular vascular network of the spinal ganglion. Semithin section. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: B, C methylene blue / azur II + basic fuchsin, D methylene blue. Abbreviation: ECN – extracapsular network, Ar - arterial vessel, P - precapillary arteriole, lymphatic capillary indicated by red arrow on fig D. Scale bar: A 100 μ m, B, C 20 μ m, D 50 μ m.

In Figure 1C within connective tissue elements of surrounded spinal ganglia detected arterial vessels with diameter not less 50 μ m. In the last image (Figure 1D) are revealed the profiles of arterioles piercing the root capsule, as well as the lymphatic capillary (shown by red arrows) with only one layer of endothelial cells in the arrangement of its walls, which attracts attention.

It should be noted that the investigation on ultrastructure of the vessels involved in the organization of the external vascular network is most

important, because of obtained information about it will determined the degree of participation of their in the flow of biological fluids. Most of the endothelial cells participant in the organization of the tunica intima of arterial vessels are bulging towards the vascular lumen with irregular nuclei on central parts and the caveolae-rich peripheral cytoplasmic parts joined with *each other through occluding junction*.

Figure 2. Electron microscopic images of the central (A) and peripheral parts (B) of the endothelial cell located in the inner layer of the extracapsular artery of the spinal ganglion and the interactions between the internal elastic membrane and smooth muscle cells situated in tunica media. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: Ar- arterial vessel, E, E1, E2, E3 -endothelial cells, IEM- internal elastic membrane, SMC- smooth muscle cells, basal lamina of endothelial cell and smooth muscle cells indicated by red single arrow. Stain: uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate. Scale bars: A 1 μ m, B 500 nm.

In experimental preparations, in all parts of the extracapsular arteries that bulge towards the vascular lumen are located the nuclei of endothelial cells. Even in preparations fixed by the intravascular perfusion method, the indentation of the edges of the indicated nuclei (Figure 2A) and the absence of noticeable changes in the endothelial cells indicate that the parts of the arterial vessels where the nuclei are located are also deformed in the experimental preparations. One of the most pressured parts of the inner layer of blood vessels are the areas was intercellular junction region

where the peripheral parts of three neighboring endothelial cells are joined to each other. One of those areas is shown in Figure 2B. The presenting a lot of number of pinocytotic vesicles of different shapes in the peripheral part of the E2 endotheliocyte, which seems to be riveted between the cells labeled with E1 and E3, the sign of macropinocytosis (marked by an arrowhead) and the formation of a myelin-like structure in the intercellular area (indicated by a double arrow) indicate the depicted area is sensitive to influence of mechanical pressure of the circulating blood.

Figure 3. Types of intercellular communication formed between endothelial cells in the extracapsular artery of spinal ganglion. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate. Abbreviation: Ar- arterial vessel, E1, E2 -endothelial cells, IEM- internal elastic membrane, ICJ -intercellular junction, GJ -gap junction, basal lamina of endothelial cell and smooth muscle cells indicated by red single arrow. Scale bar 200 nm.

In the ultrathin sections of the endothelial cells participated in the organization of the walls of the extracapsular arteries are observed different type intercellular junction (ICJ) that distinctive in relationships and structure. In Figure 3A, the peripheral parts of neighboring endothelial cells (both E1 and E2) and the finger-like projection of E1 merge with each other to form a three-layered structure. In Figure 3B, the peripheral parts of the neighboring endotheliocytes, which are not

thinned at all, have created intercellular junction, leaning on each other. The common properties in both electrograms is that the outer (external dark) layers of the plasmalemmas of neighboring cells connect with each other at certain points and form a tight junction. In comparison both slide (A and B) other differences visible between the endothelial cells that intercellular connection (cleft-shaped or nexus) composing from three layers, named gap junction (marked with GJ).

Figure 4. Electron microscopic images of the cellular and non-cellular elements involved in the wall of the extracapsular artery of the spinal ganglion. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate. Abbreviation: E1, E2, E3 -endothelial cells, IEM- internal elastic membrane, SMC- smooth muscle cells, ENT -efferent nerve terminal. Scale bar: 2 µm.

Arterial vessels differ from other vessels by having at least three layer of smooth muscle cells in their tunica media. The significant ultrastructural features of the arteries that give rise to the extra-capsular and intracapsular vascular networks of the spinal ganglia that their subendothelial regions are continuously covered by an internal elastic membrane, the tunica media is composed of at least three layers of smooth muscle cells, and the latter are in contact with the effector nerve terminal (indicated by ENT) (Fig. 4).

As a result of the accumulation of actin-myosin cytoskeleton complex mainly in the perinuclear parts of the smooth muscle cells that form the middle layer of the extracapsular arteries of the spinal ganglia there are no noticeable differences in the morphometric parameters of the latter and the central parts where located a nucleus. For example, as shown in Figure 4, the diameters of smooth muscle cells range from 2.4 μm to 2.8 μm in the nuclear regions, while the diameters of their perinuclear regions range from 2.3 μm to 3.6 μm , respectively. As can be seen from the morphometric parameters, the perinuclear part of smooth muscle cells can be a little more than the central part.

At first glance, the internal elastic membrane located in the subendothelial layer of the described vessels creates the impression that it is divided into separate fragments by means of protrusions of the endothelium and smooth muscle cells that communicate with each other (Figure 5). However, the fact that the basal lamina of the endothelium and smooth muscle cells are not detected in the regions where the described protrusions are not in contact with each other indicates that the former are located in the pores of the internal elastic membrane.

In the experimental (intact) preparations, the interruptions along of the internal elastic membranes of the arterial vessels are only revealed between the endothelial cells and the smooth muscle cells of the inner layer located close to each other (indicated by the arrow in Figure 5A) or at the level their protrusions where created myo-endothelial connections. Smooth muscle cells participating in the organization of the tunica media of the extracapsule arteries in the peripheral parts of their cytoplasm are characterized by the presence of dense bodies connected with elements of sarcolemma, caveolae, which act as a store for Ca^{2+} ions.

Figure 5. Electronogram of mutual relationship of cells composing the wall of the extracapsular arterial vessel of the spinal ganglion. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate. Abbreviation: VL -vascular lumen, E -endothelial cells, IEM- internal elastic membrane, SMC- smooth muscle cells, BM -bazement membrane. Scale bar: A 1 μm , B 500 nm, C 200 nm.

Dense bodies and caveolae are detected in the form of clusters that arranged in several rows on transverse sections of smooth muscle cells (indicated by arrows in Figure 5B). The basal lamina that surrounds the smooth muscle cells from all sides will create a three-layered basement membrane between them. A basement membrane with the same structure is also found at the points of the peripheral part of smooth muscle cells that lean against each other. Deviation from what

has been said is determined only at the level of communicating junctions (nexus) formed between the short protrusions of smooth muscle cells located in the neighbors layer (indicated by an arrow in Figure 5C). As can be seen from the electronogram, unstained areas with an amorphous structure belonging to elastic fibers revealed between the basal surfaces of neighboring smooth muscle cells (marked with an asterisk) around the nexus.

Figure 6. Demonstration of efferent nerve terminal in the wall of the extracapsular artery of the spinal ganglion. TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate. Abbreviation: ENT -efferent nerve terminal, SMC- smooth muscle cells, F- fibrocyte. Scale bar: 500 nm.

As mentioned above, one of the characteristic features of extracapsular arteries of spinal ganglia is detection of efferent nerve terminals (ENT) between their middle muscular and adventitial layers. In Figure 6, the efferent nerve terminal is located between the adventitial layer containing only one fibrocyte and the external elastic membrane fragments (shown by arrows) surrounded by smooth muscle cells. The efferent nerve terminal contains a Schwann cell fragment (below) and two axons containing mitochondria. All of the above are surrounded by the basal layer of the Schwann cell. In the cytoplasm of axons are visible centrally located round (tuberous) electron lucent vesicles. The last feature indicates that the described structures belong to the motor sympathetic nerve terminal with noradrenaline (norepinephrine) neurotransmitter in its synaptic vesicles.

Conclusion. The structural features of the cellular and non-cellular elements composing the wall of extraorganic arterial vessels participating in vascularization of spinal ganglia indicate that they have the ability

to adapt to high arterial pressure conditions, to transport vasoactive metabolites synthesized by endothelial cells in the direction of smooth muscle cells, and to change the dimensions of the vascular lumen. Finally, it should be suggested the lymphatic capillaries accompanying the arterioles, which give rise to the intraorganic vascular network are involved in the transport of protein-rich interstitial fluid from the ganglion.

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